

Corporate Governance on Strategic Management Accounting, Innovation Research Interchange Sustainability Maturity Model and Its Impact on Organizational Culture

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Abstract

This study is aiming at examining the influence of Corporate Governance (CG) on Strategic Management Accounting (SMA), IRI Sustainability Maturity Model and its impact on Organizational Culture. This study analyzes how CG influences SMA, how CG influences Sustainability Maturity Model, how SMA influences IRI Sustainability Maturity Model and the impact of IRI Sustainability Maturity Model to Organizational Culture. CG is represented by the dimensions of Independent Directors, Independent Board of Commissioners, Board of Directors and Audit Committee. SMA is represented by the Costing, Strategic Planning, Control and Performance Management, Budgeting, Strategic Decision Making, Competitor Accounting and Customer Accounting dimensions. IRI Sustainability Maturity Model is represented by dimensions of strategy and design tools while Organizational Culture is represented by Goals Achievements, Self Actualization and Humane Awards.

This study applies a mixed-method with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) data analysis techniques. This study also uses 1 (one) to 6 (six) Likert scale measure. The data used is primary data which gained from 137 respondents of 175 distributed samples. The result of the study shows that only the independent board of commissioners and board of directors as part of CG have an effect on SMA and IRI Sustainability Maturity Model. All dimensions of SMA affect the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model and all dimensions of the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model influence the Organizational Culture. Since this study only focuses on manufacturing companies, the results cannot be considered representing non-manufacturing companies. Independent directors and audit committees from the samples tend to be not playing an optimal role as agents of corporate governance. The author is unable to obtain further supporting data because of the policies in terms of company confidentiality.

For companies, they must tighten the selection of independent commissioners, independent directors and audit committees by examining each candidate's backgrounds and education, work experience and expertise. In addition, the board of directors must also give trust to independent directors and audit committees to be able to carry out their role as agents of governance in accordance with Circular Letter of the Indonesia Stock Exchange No. SE-00001/BEI/02-2014. For the government, it is better to incorporate the elements of education, work experience and expertise into regulations for those who will become stakeholders, especially independent board of commissioners, independent directors and audit committees.

If previous research emphasized on whether CG influences SMA and on how CG relates to sustainability in terms of financial statements, this study shows that IRI Sustainability Maturity Model as an intervening variable is able to show that it directly or indirectly affects Corporate Governance and Strategic Management Accounting and Organizational Culture.

Keywords: *Corporate Governance, Strategic Management Accounting, IRI Sustainability Maturity Model and Organizational Culture*

Background of the research

Economic growth is an indication of success in Indonesia's economic development. Therefore, various ways have been taken by the government so that economic growth and development in Indonesia are sustainable. Policies that lead to the development of various industries continue to be encouraged so that the industrial growth and the economic flow are maintained, and finally trigger economic growth. One industry that continues to be encouraged to keep growing is the manufacturing industry. This is because the industry is able to grow and accumulate wealth to encourage strong economic capitalization and foundation (Obioma, 2015). So that it is very reasonable, Indonesia as a large developing country in the Southeast Asia continues to push industrialization in the manufacturing sector to support the level of economic growth in Indonesia. As reported by the Ministry of Industry of the Republic of Indonesia, Airlangga Hartarto, Manufacture industry gives a big contribution to Indonesia economic income (thejakartapost.com)

However, from 2011 to 2015, the growth rate tendency of the manufacturing sector continued to decrease from the targeted growth rate (Faisal Basri, 2015). The growth rate of the manufacturing sector industry in Indonesia especially in 2017 below than macro-economic growth from the targeted growth rate (www.indonesia-investment.com). Moreover, according to Hariyadi Sukamdani (2017) as General Chair of the Employers' Association of Indonesia (Apindo), the downward trend in purchasing power is strongly influenced by and influences the absorption rate of formal labor. According to data sources from the Social Security Administrative Bodies (BPJS), the period of absorption of formal labor from 2010 to 2016 is only 850,000 people every year, even though around 2 million people enter the labor market every year. The imbalance between the number of the workforce and the labor absorption

affects the decline in people's purchasing power. Influenced by the decreasing level of industrial growth in the manufacturing sector, the level of inequality is increased. Another factor is the decline in purchasing power encouraging people, especially the middle class, to hold back spending and tend to save or save money (www.kompas.com). These factors influence the decline of the manufacturing sector growth in Indonesia. Furthermore, the manufacturing industry in the world is ready to welcome 4.0 industrial revolution including Indonesia. To become persist in the industrial market, the company has to produce innovative products. Innovative itself came from the pattern of thinking of the people in the industrial company that very dynamic and artistic in organizations (Amabile,1983, 1998; Amabile et al., 1996) . M.A. Musa et., all (2008) stated that innovation can be created from solid team work in the company including the participation of the board of directors. Since the board of the directors is the one that has a very important role to initiate innovation in the company

Based on the above phenomena, companies in this sector face the pressure so that the company's business capabilities can continue to exist, survive and be able to gain profits, in addition to facing increasingly fierce industrial competition. Management of various company-owned resources and maintenance of corporate communications with various related parties for business and operational performance survive must be carried out effectively so that the company remains sustainable.

Several factors influence the process of implementing the sustainability maturity model. In order to have effective, efficient and maximum planning, implementation and supervision of the sustainability maturity model, Corporate governance is playing the important rule. According to Lawrence, S., Collins, E. & Roper, J. (2013), The success level for the company sustainability is extensively affected by corporate governance characteristics. Moreover, CG is the mode in which an organization is aimed at, controlled and administrated (Haider et al., 2015). CG identifies policy practices and procedures as well as helps the making of accurate policy for various corporate issues and affairs. Through this, CG offers a composition by which organizational goals are developed and adopt s creative methods to achieve these objectives through sustainable monitoring performance. Furthermore, CG is expected to to bring out the interest of corporate clients including the investors and make sure that the corporate aim is to maximize the profit for investors (Haider et al., 2015). Corporate governance is a base for company achievement and plays important rules for company strategic activity (Varshney, P., Kaul, V.K. & Vasal, V.K., 2013). Besides that, the main goals of CG are the develop- ment of corporate culture by maximizing performance to motivate the board of directors, entrepreneurs and managers in an effort to improve efficiency and maintain long cycle performance or high profitability with the longest cycle. Therefore, profitability is very influential and influenced by CG activity (Akhtar, 2006) . Consequently, one of the positive impacts of implementing effective CG is the ability to increase the company's goals towards a more sustainable company that is mediated by high profitability. The stability of the CG mechanism activities can be measured from the optimal roles of independent directors, independent commissioners, directors and audit committees (Arunruangsirilert and Chonglertham, 2017).

This research focus to use The IRI Sustainability Maturity Model as a sustainability model. CG has a vital role to make the company sustain in the future (Srivastava et al.,2018).

The IRI SMM is a concept of a sustainability maturity model in which the organization involves Research & Development (R & D) and New Product Development (NPD) functions. This model consists of 14 indicators which can be grouped in to two focus areas: design tools and strategy tools. These two focus areas facilitate differentiation between planning and infrastructure activities of the strategy section and tactical activities of the design tool section. This IRI SMM can change the growth model of a dimensional matrix into a device that facilitates organizations to benchmark their sustainability performance during new product development (NPD). The tool helps organizations to identify activities and opportunities in the field to meet the sustainability goals of the company. Mapping and analysis of this sustainability matrix model provide capabilities for companies to maximize the achievement of long term company goals.

The most basic explanation of the relationship between CG and IRI SMM based on the goal of CG is to maximize shareholder wealth that can be measured from the high level of profitability that can be obtained by the company. On the other hand, IRI SMM is a sustainability model which can be applied and helps companies to achieve high profitability with its orientation to long term sustainability and growth through the use of R & D functions and NPD programs to optimize company opportunities related to market demand in relation to analysis of community, market and consumer behaviors so that the company's business performance can continue to be highly sustainable. In this case, the high profitability obtained by the company can provide a great opportunity for management to capture various potential and opportunities for current and future market changes to expand so that the company's performance is on a high level sustainable stage. Although on the other hand, the high level of profitability of the company can be a potential conflict between shareholders regarding the earnings policy—whether the company prioritizes retained earnings to increase growth and expansion or prioritize dividend distribution which of course can reduce the potential for future company expansion. Apart from these conflicts of interest, this explanation proves that the link between CG and IRI SMM is inevitable.

Another factor that influences sustainability maturity or in the context of this research termed as IRI SMM is

SMA. As a concept, SMA can be defined as a business strategy that includes two key strategies namely business strategy and functional strategy. SMA as a business strategy has been aimed at achieving the target of the company and winning a fairly competitive business competition which ultimately can maintain the existence and sustainability of the company. While SMA as a functional strategy has been aimed at carrying out various actions at a more specific level. Business strategy can be said as an integrated and purposeful action and has a target to win a competitive and sustainable market—to obtain a sustainable competitive advantage. SMA also paid attention to internal resources element and organization capability to support external competence based (Nixon & Burns, 2012; Tayles et al., 2002; Tayles et al., 2007). Moreover, the application of SMA will succeed if it relates to company vision and mission based (Agwu ME, 2018).

The relationship between SMA and IRI SMM is based on company activities in an effort to implement strategic policies and practices through examinations on various strategic analysis such as financing, budgeting, consumer analysis, competition analysis. Other strategic analysis which can be helped and is closely related to effective practices during the implementation of IRI SMM through the implementation of design and design tools in the utilization of research and development (R & D) and new product development (NPD) of the company. This is because, as revealed by Hynds et al. (2014), IRI SMM models and frameworks are based on R & D and NPD development in IRI SMM, which in practice produces special divisions delegated to the utilization of R & D and NPD. , whose duty is to make developments analysis and reports related to both the capabilities of the company and the external analysis of the company related to opportunities and challenges, which will later become a reference for companies in achieving the company's goals to be more effective, efficient and maximum, which in the end the company's performance in the long term is more sustainable.

The encouragement and pressure on the measurements and analysis of the company's strategic steps in the SMA context are also influenced by CG's control and supervision function so that the company is highly sustainable. So that there is a very close relationship between CG and SMA, where the benefits of SMA today are very important in helping the practice of corporate governance because the era of industrial moderation requires the control of operations, which certainly can maintain the company's competitive advantage (Tuomela, 2005). SMA can have a significant role in the company's strategic operations (Wickramasinghe and Alawattage, 2007). One example is the benefits of SMA for investors, in which high schools can provide a collection of devices that worker processes can be scrutinized remotely by arranging them into cost accounting systems. Evidence of SMA application in governance also appears in the enterprise governance (EG) framework. SMA plays an important role that can provide tools effectively and support strategic governance practices. Hence SMA will be optimized with strategically improved CG (Arunruangsirilert and Chonglertham, 2017).

Based on the correlation between CG and SMA, CG and IRI SMM, SMA with IRI SMM therefore, the three variables are strongly related and influence each other. The relationship between CG, SMA and IRI SMM is based on the fact that CG demands the maximization of shareholder wealth through optimization and effectiveness of operating controls, IRI SMM provides R & D and NPD functions as design and design tools to capture opportunities during business expansion so that highly sustainable company performance can be maintained for long term and SMA acts as measurement tools and strategic analysis that can provide references so that company decisions are strategic in achieving goals through optimizing high performance and high conformance. In other words, SMA can bridge the gap in corporate issues because the resulting strategic decisions can improve company performance. This departs from the issues raised by the International Federation Accountant (IFAC) (2004) which propose an enterprise governance (EG) framework to address the gap between CG and business governance (BG). EG provides a guideline for accountability for organizations to balance two different branches of governance, namely CG and business governance (BG). This framework suggests that the balance of CG and BG will encourage conformance and great performance. In addition, SMA is a supporter of corporate governance, which according to Cadez and Guilding (2012) can play an important role in improving the business performance of a company. The important role of the management accounting control system is based on the magnitude of opportunities and opportunities for organizations to continually improve performance development strategies in order to achieve high-standard quality business activities through improved learning capabilities and better organizational sensitivity (Schiller, 2010), and thus help the organization to continue to improve the quality of optimal performance following rapid changes in the environment (Jakobsen, 2012)

The significance of this research for companies is to emphasize the important role of SMA in the context of governance which is then associated with IRI SMM and the impact of IRI SMM on organizational culture. According to Arunruangsirilert and Chonglertham (2017), more and more companies are paying great attention to good corporate governance (CG) issues, which is considered can serve as "tools" of control that can guarantee the operation and performance of a business company. According to IFAC (2004), one of the ways and work process of corporate governance is through the use of strategic management accounting (SMA) which plays a role of providing guidance and direction for company's business achievement and value creation through management support in strategy and control perspectives . Therefore, the expected contribution of this research for companies is providing valuable information and knowledge to the manager about the use of SMA for each CG characteristic. This expectation arises

based on the link between CG, SMA which is associated with IRI SMM and its relationship with organizational culture within the governance framework as a strategic framework rarely analyzed in the previous studies.

Based on the relationships between these variables, this study seeks to raise the title: "Analysis of the Effect of Corporate Governance on Strategic Management Accounting, IRI Sustainability Maturity Model and Its impact on Organizational Culture"

Based on the formulation of the problem above, the objectives of this study are:

1. To analyze the influence of independent directors, independent commissioners, directors, and audit committees on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.
2. To analyze the influence of the influence of Independent Directors, Independent Board of Commissioners, Board of Directors, and Audit Committee on Usage of Strategic Management Accounting in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.
3. To analyze the influence of Strategic Costing, Strategic Planning, Control and Performance, Budgeting, Strategic Decision-Making, Competitor Accounting and Customer Accounting (SMA) on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.
4. To analyze the influence of the strategies and design tools of the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model on Organizational Culture in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

Literature Review

Corporate governance describes a system that governs a company based on agency theory (Huillier, 2014). Through the use of Corporate Governance, it is hoped that it can provide positive thinking to investors—they believe will get investment returns in accordance with their expectations (Mulcahy and Donnelly, 2015). Corporate governance has to do with investors. If the implementation of Corporate Governance in a company has run well, it is expected that investors will get a return that fits their expectations. Investors are also sure if the company manager will not commit embezzlement or invest outside the knowledge of investors, besides that Corporate Governance also regulates how investors control the the managers (Choudry and Hoque, 2006).

Indonesia Good Corporate Governance General Guidelines is a role model for all companies in Indonesia, including companies adopting sharia principles. The implementation of Good Corporate Governance is intended to ensure good corporate sustainability based on the principles of transparency, independence, responsibility, accountability and equality (Michael and Goo , 2015). To urge the functions and independence of each company organization such as the board of commissioners, directors and general meeting of shareholders, the decisions and actions taken must be based on high moral values and comply with applicable legal regulations (Guo, Smallman and Radford, 2013) .

There are many dimensions involved in measuring CG but this study is limited to dimensions adapted from Arunruangsiriliert and Chonglertham (2017), namely:

1. Independent director
2. Independent board of commissioners
3. Board of directors
4. Audit committee.

SMA is a comprehensive and integrative concept that emerges from various perspectives (Shah et al., 2011) such as marketing focus (Roslender and Hart, 2002), future orientation (Wilson, 1995), competitor perspective (Guilding, 1999), nonfinancial components (Chenhall and Langfield-Smith, 2003), and total quality management (TQM) (Khan and Jain, 2007). In summary, SMA can be defined in two aspects; the aspects of strategic management accounting usage (SMAU) and the strategic management accounting participation (SMAP) (Shareia, 2015).

SMAU must fulfill two conditions of strategic implications, namely a future-oriented and long-term time frame and an externally focused perspective (Cadez & Guilding, 2012). From these two conditions, there are 16 SMAU arranged in five broader categories: costing; planning, control, and measurement of performance; decision making; customer accounting; and competitors accounting. Meanwhile, SMAP is the participation of accountants which is an important factor in strategic management. From this perspective, Cadez and Guilding (2012) see accounting involvement no longer seen as an information provider, but they are considered active actors in SMAP. In a consumer-orientation strategy, accountants must act according to the horizontal value chain of the organization so that they can react effectively with high competition (Chenhall & Langfield-Smith, 2003). Accountants respond to the need for management satisfaction in potentially competitive and diverse goals.

SMA measurement refers to Arunruangsiriliert and Chonglertham (2017), which are added to the budgeting dimension for measuring SMA, so that the dimensions involve:

1. Strategic Costing
2. Strategic Planning, Control and Performance Management
3. Strategic Decision Making

4. Competitor Accounting
5. Customer Accounting
6. Budgeting

Sustainability is no longer associated with consumer trends and has now become an important consideration in business (Hynds et al., 2014). This has led many companies to continue to show interest in sustainability integration into their business (Haaneas et al., 2011). Many factors support companies to adopt sustainability practices, including the need for regulations compliance or anticipation of regulatory changes, understanding of limited natural resources, consumer demand and interests or hopes to limit costs associated with resource consumption and garbage disposal. The factors that control and influence the company are very real that as reported by the Sloan Management Report, companies believe sustainability will slowly become a core function that is central to business success (Haaneas et al., 2011).

The IRI sustainability maturity model mainly focuses on the activities used by Research & Development (R & D) and NPD functions or activities used by other functions that support technology research and NPD. The model consists of 14 dimensions arranged in two focus areas: design tools and strategy tools. These two focuses facilitate differentiation between planning and infrastructure activities from the strategy section and tactical activities of the design tool section. Technical functions - engineering design, R & D, or manufacturing engineering - appear in the design tool section, while strategy activities can involve a variety of functions, including the executive team, product management, legal department and others.

The measurement of IRI Sustainability Maturity Model (IRI-SMM) refers to research conducted by Hynds et al., (2014) which measures it with two key dimensions, namely the dimensions of strategy and dimensions of design devices. Detailed descriptions of these dimensions are as follows:

1. Dimension of strategy
2. Dimensions of design devices

Organizational culture is the understanding of experts, on which they agree if the organizational culture is able to bind all parties in the organization to pay attention to the values of life because the values of life certainly affect an organization. Robbins and Judge (2015) explained that organizational culture refers to a system which is understood and adopted by all members so that the organization is different from other organizations. Having a system understood by all members means that the organization has a characteristic and this characteristic is upheld by the organization. Organizational culture is the controller and guide in shaping the attitudes and behavior of members within an organization. Individually or in the group a person cannot be separated from the culture of the organization and in general the members of the organization are influenced by the diversity of existing resources.

Robbins and Judge (2015) stated that organizational culture is a system in which the philosophy is perceived equally by each member and used together in the organization so that the organization has different characteristics from other organizations. So organizational culture is a system created and developed by the organization based on the form of habits and basic philosophy of the founder, which ultimately creates a rule which is used as a guide / philosophy of the company in achieving organizational goals. A strong culture will be able to spur better organizational development.

The dimensions used to distinguish organizational culture, according to Robbins and Judge (2015), are manifested in seven main characteristics that collectively capture the nature of organizational culture, namely:

- 1) Renewal and risk taking.
- 2) Pay attention to detailed things. Viewed from the perspective of accuracy, analysis, and attention to details.
- 3) Focus on results. Management pays attention to the results not to the process or technique used in obtaining these results.
- 4) Human oriented. To what extent the management decisions affect individuals in the organization.
- 5) Team oriented. Forming a good and solid team work.
- 6) Group work team.
- 7) Aggressiveness. Establish an aggressive and competitive work culture.
- 8) Steadiness. Sustainability

Framework Development

The framework of this study is as follows:

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis Development

The hypotheses in this study are as follows:

- H₁: Independent directors have a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₂: Independent Commissioners have a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₃: The board of directors has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₄: Audit committee has a positive effect on IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₅: Independent directors have a positive effect on the Usage of Strategic Management Accounting.
- H₆: Independent Commissioners have a positive effect on the Usage of Strategic Management Accounting.
- H₇: The board of directors has a positive influence on the Usage of Strategic Management Accounting.
- H₈: Audit committee has a positive effect on the Usage of Strategic Management Accounting.
- H₉: Strategic Costing has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model
- H₁₀: Strategic Planning, Control and Performance has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₁₁: Budgeting has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₁₂: Strategic Decision-Making has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model
- H₁₃: Competitor Accounting has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₁₄: Customer Accounting has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model.
- H₁₅: IRI Strategy Sustainability Maturity Model has a positive effect on organizational culture
- H₁₆: The design tools of the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model have a positive effect on organizational culture

Research Methodology

This research is mixed method research, in which qualitative data is processed and converted into quantitative form. According to Sugiyono (2011), to produce a valid, reliable, comprehensive and objective, a research activity can be combined through qualitative and quantitative research and the suitable method for this is a mixed method.

The data analysis technique in this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Consideration of the SEM analysis application is the variable of Corporate Governance, Usage of Strategic Management Accounting, and IRI Sustainability and Organizational Culture are unobserved variables, since they are represented by their forming dimensions. The contribution of each dimension to the variables used is certainly not the same weight so the use of SEM is more appropriate than the regression equation. In this Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), a dependent variable in one particular equation can be an independent variable in another equation. In this case, we will see the influence of the dimensions of Corporate Governance, and Usage of Strategic Management Accounting, on IRI Sustainability. Then we will look at the effect of IRI Sustainability on Organizational Culture. So that in the end it will be known the role of IRI in creating Organizational Sustainability and Culture.

The sample used in this study was 137 respondents from 175 samples. The size of this sample was obtained from the members of the board of directors, the board of the commissioners, independent chairman and the audit committee of several manufacturing companies found on the IDX

Analysis Results

All data in this study have been tested for validity and reliability. The results show that the questionnaire item in the study is valid and reliable.

The following is a model match size criteria (GOF) list that is used to test the overall model

Table 4.5. The goodness of Fit Model Test Results

Type of Measurement	Measurement	Recommended Acceptance Limit	Value	Decision
Absolute Fit Measure	<i>Chi-square</i>	$X^2 \text{ hit} < X^2 \text{ Table (df = 734)}$	1428,81	<i>Good Fit</i>
	<i>p-value</i>	≥ 0.05	0.007	<i>Good Fit</i>
	RMSEA	≤ 0.10	0.074	<i>Good Fit</i>
	GFI	≥ 0.90 or close to number 1	0.941	<i>Good Fit</i>
Incremental Fit Measures	NFI	≥ 0.90 or close to number 1	0.96	<i>Good Fit</i>
	IFI	≥ 0.90 or close to number 1	0.98	<i>Good Fit</i>
	RFI	≥ 0.90 or close to number 1	0.96	<i>Good Fit</i>
	CFI	≥ 0.90 or close to number 1	0.98	<i>Good Fit</i>
	AGFI	≥ 0.90 or close to number 1	0.97	<i>Good Fit</i>
Parsimonious Fit Measure	<i>Normed Chi Square</i>	Lower limit 1, upper limit 5.	1.9466	<i>Good Fit</i>

On the above table it can be seen that Absolute Fit Measure RMSEA value is categorized as Good Fit with a value of 0.074 which is almost close to the value of 0.10. Furthermore, the Incremental Fit Measures criteria can be fulfilled. This can be seen from the values of NFI, IFI, RFI, CFI and AGFI of 0.96; 0.98; 0.96; 0.98 and 0.97 which are in the Good Fit category. The criteria based on Parsimonious Fit Measure by looking at the Normed chi square value with a value of 1.9466 that meets the lower boundary conditions 1 and upper limit 5. Therefore it can be concluded that there are criteria that meet the Good Fit Model and this model deserves further investigation, because the indicator that shows good fit.

Result and Discussion

Table 4.6. Partial Hypothesis Testing Results (t Test)

Model	β Coefficient	Sig.	Result
Independent Director → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,076	0,231	H _{a1} rejected
Independent Board of Commissioners → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,271	0,021	H _{a2} supported
Board of Directors → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,583	0,019	H _{a3} supported
Audit Committee → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,062	0,117	H _{a4} rejected
Independent Director → Strategic Management Accounting	0,013	0,104	H _{a5} rejected
Independent Board of Commissioners → Strategic Management Accounting	0,318	0,004	H _{a6} supported
Board of Directors → Strategic Management Accounting	0,215	0,012	H _{a7} supported
Audit Committee → Strategic Management Accounting	0,041	0,230	H _{a8} rejected
Costing → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,350	0,000	H _{a9} supported
Strategic Planning, Control & Performance → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,372	0,000	H _{a10} supported
Budgeting → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,298	0,000	H _{a11} supported
Strategic Decision Making → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,155	0,008	H _{a12} supported
Competitor Accounting → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,712	0,000	H _{a13} supported
Customer Accounting → IRI Sustainability Maturity Model	0,383	0,002	H _{a14} supported
Strategy IRI Sustainability Maturity Model → Organizational Culture	0,447	0,000	H _{a15} supported
Design Tools IRI Sustainability Maturity Model → Organizational Culture	0,405	0,000	H _{a16} supported

The Effect of Corporate Governance on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

Effect of Independent Directors on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The significance value of the Independent Director's p-value on the IRI sustainability maturity model of 0.231 is greater than the alpha (α) value of 5 percent. This means that Independent Directors do not significantly influence the IRI sustainability maturity model. This happens because the independent director has a strong affiliation with the company's directors and commissioners. So that the role of an independent director who should be an organ of corporate governance can no longer be represented. The existence of these affiliates influences the role of independent directors in representing the public interest, namely to maintain the interests of minority shareholders to get fair treatment.

If the decision of the independent director has been influenced by members of the board of directors and commissioners, the strategic planning and design tools that have been compiled are biased. The company's sustainability then is disrupted due to bias from long-term planning. Dalton, Daily, Ellstrand, and Johnson (1998) stated that there was no relationship between the presence of independent directors and company performance. Krause and Semadeni (2013) also stated that the presence of independent directors in general did not give too much influence on improving company performance. This is also supported by research conducted by Stanford University Corporate Governance Research Initiatives, one of which states that independent directors are not strong enough to be used as an indicator of improving the quality of company performance.

The results of this study are in line with the findings of the study of Bhagat & Black, 2002; Brick & Chidambaran, 2010; Topak, 2011; Hermalin & Weisbach, 1991; Rodríguez et al., 2013 which explain that there is no correlation between the involvement of independent directors in improving the quality of performance, as measured by the company's growth sustainability.

Effect of Independent Commissioners on IRI Sustainability Models

Independent Commissioners have a positive effect on IRI Sustainability maturity model. Viewed from the significance value of the p-value of 0.021 which is smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05. The greater the size of the board of commissioners of a company, the greater the sustainability of the company. On the contrary the lower the size of the board of commissioners of a company, the lower the sustainability level of the company. Dwi Putra (2015) stated in his research that independent commissioners have an effect on improving company performance, especially the impact on ROE as in the study findings of Prantama et al., (2012). So the higher the proportion of the number of independent commissioners in a company, the better the performance of the company.

The results of the interview also indicated that the commissioners were very instrumental in maintaining corporate governance. Kosnik (1990) suggests that the role of independent commissioners is more effective than commissioners from within the company. So that it can be said that the better independent commissioners performance, the greater the level of sustainability of the company is achieved. This is because the duties and responsibilities of the board of commissioners in overseeing the performance of the company and also maintaining wider interests, not only in the interests of the majority shareholders, but also minority shareholders, other stakeholders including employees, consumers, the public, non-governmental organizations, the government and other stakeholders can run well. This is also in accordance with the rules of the Financial Services Authority No. 33 / POJK.04 / 2014 regarding the role of the independent board of commissioners. So that if independent commissioners maintain their independence, all interests of the broader stakeholders are maintained and in the end the company's business existence is maintained and supported by all stakeholders, which slowly but surely encourage long-term sustainability of the company.

Effect of the Board of Directors on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The results of statistical tests have shown that the significance value of p-value for the board of directors is 0.019 smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05. This means that the board of directors has a positive effect on the IRI sustainability maturity model. Mizruchi (1983) in Midiastuti and Mackfudz (2003) explained that the center of the company's operations is on the control of the board of directors because the main obligations of the Board of Directors are to keep the company sustainability in the future.

As a result, the higher the performance of a company's board of directors, the greater the sustainability of the company, and vice versa. The lower the performance of a company's board of directors, the smaller the level of sustainability of the company. This is also in line with Yudha Prawira & Haryanto (2015) conclusion that the board of directors has an influence on improving company performance.

In addition, the interview results also indicate that the board of directors has considerable power in managing the company. This is in line with the Financial Services Authority rules No. 33./POJK.04/2014 regarding directors and commissioners of listed companies in Indonesia. This is because the duties, functions and responsibilities of the board of directors in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia are optimal in synergizing all the interests of both commissioners, independent commissioners and stakeholders more broadly so as to assist the board of directors in terms of leadership, determination of important policies, monitoring and evaluating employee performance, company annual budgeting and reporting to shareholders. The ability of the board of directors to absorb and accommodate all

the aspirations of the shareholders and stakeholders and their application when supervising the company's operational managers influences the company's capability in terms of meeting the needs of the wider community in pursuit of corporate sustainability. Makhoul et al., (2017) who have proven that the more effective the performance of the board of directors, the better the performance of the company, including the greater the opportunity for the company's business growth.

This research shows that the board of directors is able to explain that stakeholders and shareholders are quite satisfied with the accountability of the board of directors with regard to performance reports on companies in the manufacturing sector in Indonesia. This reinforces the role of CG for manufacturing companies to provide control through control mechanisms that do not only rely on the interests of shareholders but also rely on the interests of stakeholders more broadly.

The influence of the Audit Committee has a positive effect on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The results of this study indicate that the audit committee has no significant effect on the IRI of the sustainability maturity model in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. This can be seen from the significance value of p-value of 0.117 greater than alpha (α) of 0.05 (H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected). This means that the audit committee has no significant effect on the IRI sustainability maturity model. The company sustainability is not influenced by decisions made by the audit committee. This is also supported by Sri Wijayanti and Siti Mutmainah (2012) and Maria Fransiska Widyati (2013) who stated that the audit committee has no influence in the company's financial performance. In addition, Nicholas J. Prize (2018) also stated that the audit committee only focuses on matters relating to financial reporting, especially those related to the accounting process and internal control systems of the company. So that it is clearly seen if the audit committee does not play a role in matters related to the company's strategic policies.

The Audit Committee in the company is the representative of the Independent Commissioner especially in terms of information audits and corporate financial performance. This is in accordance with Kep-117 / M-MBU / 2002 regarding the functions of the audit committee. Even so, in the implementation, the parties that make decisions related to the company's operations are the Board of Directors in accordance with the Financial Services Authority regulations No. 33 / POJK.04 / 2014. Then often there is a conflict of interest between the Independent Commissioners and the Board of Directors. Roles, functions, tasks and responsibilities of the audit committee are more emphasized on information audits and corporate financial performance only. Then the existence and duties of the audit committee more influence the performance of the company in the short term but not on the long-term performance of corporate sustainability. Bassiouny (2016) emphasized that there is a close relationship between audit quality and company performance, which is based on high-quality audits trying to find and report errors in the financial reporting of audited companies. Some reasons include the auditor's reputation for maximum audit results and tend to not be able to compromise with errors or manipulations on the financial reporting of the audited company. Also supported by Swastika (2013), audit quality plays an important role in management monitoring to protect the interests of shareholders. So that the demand for auditors to produce a more independent, more competent and high integrity audit has underpinned their audit activities related to the demands of independence and objectivity.

Effect of Corporate Governance on Strategic Management Accounting

Effect of Independent Directors on Usage of Strategic Management Accounting

The results of statistical tests have shown a significance value of p-value of 0.104 that exceeds the value of alpha (α) 0.05. This means that independent directors have no significant effect on strategic management accounting. The decisions of independent directors are ineffective and not independent in implementing good corporate governance.

This shows that independent directors in carrying out their duties are not as independent as expected by shareholders. This, therefore, shows that the independent director does not play any role in implementing strategic management accounting in manufacturing companies in Indonesia. According to the Agency theory paradigm of Jensen and Meckling (1976), the implementation of independent CG can control management as an agent to work in accordance with the interests of shareholders so that agents remain focused on company performance. The focus of work of managers in running the day-to-day operations of companies to meet the interests of shareholders does not encourage high awareness on the importance of implementing strategic management accounting to improve long-term company performance.

Based on the results of the interview, this study confirms that the independent director in making his decision is still strongly influenced by the board of directors, so that the decisions set by the independent director indirectly are the decisions desired by the board of directors. Krause & Semadeni (2013) stated that the presence of independent directors in general does not give too much influence on improving company performance.

Effect of Independent Commissioners on Usage of Strategic Management Accounting

The results of statistical tests have shown that the significance value of p-value for the sixth hypothesis is

0.004 which is smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05. This means that the independent commissioners board has a positive effect on the usage of strategic management accounting.

The greater the number of independent commissioners board of a company, the higher the level of effectiveness and level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance. On the contrary, the lower the number of independent commissioners boards of a company, the lower the level of effectiveness and the level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance (Brayendwi putra, 2015).

In addition, the results of the interviews also indicate the active role of independent commissioners in implementing corporate governance. Honggowati et al., (2017) who have proven that good governance, which includes high and positive involvement of independent commissioners in carrying out their duties and functions, can improve the effective application of corporate strategic management accounting. The greater the number of independent commissioners board of a company, the higher the level of effectiveness and level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance. On the contrary, the lower the number of independent commissioners board of a company, the lower the effectiveness and level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance (Putra, 2015).

This is in accordance with the application of good corporate governance, in which the task of independent commissioners board always adopts the interests of a broader range of stakeholders so that they ultimately encourage strategic management practices. Their duties specifically are ensuring transparency and openness of the company's financial statements to seek fair treatment of minority shareholders and other stakeholders. Other contributions from independent commissioners to the importance of implementing strategic management accounting are making and delivering rational and prudent considerations, with which an independent commissioner has the right to express opinions that are different from other board members and their opinions are recorded in the Minutes of the Board of Commissioners and if their opinions are different materially, it must be included in the Annual Report.

In addition, the criteria of independent commissioners candidates in order to carry out their roles optimally also affect the emphasis on implementing strategic management accounting. Criteria of independence from all interests encourage decision that encourages companies to be oriented towards long-term business performance results through the implementation of strategic management accounting. So as confirmed by Arunruangsirilet and Chonglertham, (2017) that the larger size of independent commissioners can positively influence the implementation of SMA, the larger number of independent commissioners will demand more strategic information as a way to effectively and efficiently monitor the organization.

Effect of the Board of Directors on Usage of Strategic Management Accounting

The statistical test results show that the significance value of p-value obtained is 0.012 smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05. This means that the board of directors has a positive and significant influence on strategic management accounting. The greater the size of the board of directors of a company, the higher the level of effectiveness and level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance (Widyati, 2013) and Yudha Prawira, Haryanto (2015). The lower the size of a company's board of directors, the lower the level of effectiveness and level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance.

These statistical test results show the fact that is in line with the viewpoints and paradigms of Agency theory and Stewardship theory. Stewardship theory from Donaldson and Davis (1991) emphasizes that the activity of the board of directors as indicated by the increasing frequency of board meetings, board attendance, and other board activities will require more strategic information during decision making to achieve good performance to meet the expectations of the stakeholders and shareholders. In this case, SMA plays an important role in providing strategic information for the board of directors to follow the corporate governance framework (IFAC, 2004). So as has been proven in this study, the board of directors has a positive effect on the usage of strategic management accounting. As confirmed by Honggowati et al., (2017), Widyawati & Haryanto (2015) that the board of directors is the main key in translating the wishes and expectations of the board of commissioners which are then translated and delegated to management. So that the ability to adopt and translate the expectations of the board of commissioners leads the board of directors to implement strategic management accounting practices.

This statistical finding is also supported by the findings of the interview which is stating that the board of directors can account for performance reports to stakeholders & shareholders, supporting the General Meeting of Shareholders, carry out the company's duties well and prepare the financial statements properly. By showing this the board of directors has carried out their duties in determining the company's strategic policy in the field of financing, both the financing, marketing and branding strategies of the company's products well.

Effect of the Audit Committee on Usage of Management Accounting

The significance value of p-value is 0.230 greater than alpha (α) of 0.05. This indicates that the audit committee's decision does not affect the effectiveness and level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance. In addition, it also shows that audit committee decisions do not affect the effectiveness

and level of independence of the company in implementing good corporate governance.

The limited and short-term orientated role of the audit committee on overall corporate performance does not have the capacity and authority to propose views that can improve the effectiveness of corporate strategy implementation. The audit committee also does not have the duty and authority to implement strategic management accounting practices. As confirmed by Bassiouny (2016) that the audit committee only focuses on high-quality audits that try to find and report errors in the audited company financial report, using audit standards.

The absence of a connection between the audit committee and strategic management accounting as concluded from the interview results of this study shows that the performance of the audit committee is more influenced by the board of directors than the board of commissioners even though the audit committee is considered a representative of the board of commissioners but for routine matters in carrying out company activities then the board of directors has more role. Mizruchi (1983) in Midiastuti and Mackfudz (2003) explained that the center control of the company's operations is on the board of directors. With this role one of the main obligations of the Board of Directors is to keep the company sustainable in the future. So that the performance of the audit committee related to the company's strategy is strongly influenced by the board of directors or the board of directors.

Effect of Strategic Management Accounting on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

Effect of Strategic Costing on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The p-value significance value of 0,000 is smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05. Then the costing strategy has a positive and significant effect on the IRI sustainability maturity model. The higher the quality of strategic financing analysis applied in a company, the higher the sustainability of the company, on the contrary the lower the quality of analysis of strategic financing applied in a company, the lower the sustainability level of the company. Alsoboa et al., (2015) explained that strategic financing has a positive effect on company performance. This positive effect can be shown by the sustainability level of the company.

This is also in line with Cyntia (2015) argument that costing strategies were positively significant influencing organizational performance and competitive advantage. Because strategic financing can provide an opportunity for management to determine how precisely and accurately the costing policy is through an analysis that compares the various cost components of a paid price for the right raw material at the price consumers paid for finished goods. Advanced skills in the analysis of costs can be a competitive advantage of the company that enables companies to survive in the market and continue to show growth performance. Heralova (2017), explains that strategic costing can increase opportunities in providing information on the quality of financing, so that it can reduce operational costs significantly (Heralova, 2017). Therefore strategic costing can also encourage effectiveness in improving policy quality in determining the costs that can then add to the competitive advantage for the company (Cynthia & Devie, 2015), which then affects the sustainability of the company.

Effect of Strategic Planning, Control and Performance on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The results of statistical tests have shown that the p-value significance for this hypothesis is 0,000 which is smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05. This means that Strategic planning, control and performance have a positive and significant effect on the IRI the sustainability maturity model. The higher the quality of the implementation of strategic planning, control systems and performance systems applied in a company, the higher the level of sustainability of the company. On the contrary, the lower the quality of the implementation of strategic planning.

This is because the performance strategy focuses on the extent to which performance planning, and its implementation can be realized so that it becomes appropriate and fit the stringent quality standards. In this case, the role of supervision or control can direct the ongoing performance to be evaluated from time to time to fit the planned goals. The strict effort to adjustment of the planning, supervision and performance that is taking place encourages changes to the ways and methods towards high-standard performance standards. According to Goh & Richards (1997), the process of environmental learning both externally and internally over the implementation of performance through the process of benchmarking, integrated performance measurement and measurement of material flow accounting conducted by the company provides higher capabilities for the company. This eventually makes the company has a chance to continue the opportunities growing their business to obtain opportunities in the future.

Based on the results and findings of the interviews, this study also proves that the impact of strategic planning, implementation and supervision can help companies in a matter related to material flow cost accounting. Marota et al., (2015) also stated that there was a sufficiently significant influence on MFCA (one of the accounting models used as strategic planning, control and performance) for corporate sustainability. This made it easier for companies to run a control system for performance. The measurement of material cash flows from the start of the planning has been well controlled, which provides all kinds of planning information that can be the basic capital for users of information as a reference to see the direction of the company's performance.

Effects of Budgeting on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

Viewed from its significance value with a p-value of 0,000 which is smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05, budgeting has a positive and significant effect on the IRI the sustainability maturity model. The higher the quality of strategic budgeting analysis applied in a company, the higher the sustainability level of the company, on the contrary the lower the quality of strategic budgeting analysis applied in a company, the lower the sustainability level of the company. Therefore an effective budget policy of a company is very dependent on the ability of management to obtain a wide range of information, abundant and accurate so as to provide many choices for management to determine what strategic budgeting policy steps can provide a high level of effectiveness and efficiency for the company. The statement is also in line with Risa (2014) and Putra (2015) who stated that it requires a high commitment from budget makers to avoid budget gaps. Where according to Popesko et al., (2017) if effective corporate budgeting can positively and significantly influence the performance of the company then it can increase the growth and sustainability of the company.

The results and findings of interviews have shown that companies in the manufacturing sector are very diverse with regard to budgeting policies from a centralistic or decentralized perspective. Some companies show the effectiveness and high efficiency implementation of centralized budgeting policies while others are considered effective and efficient with high decentralization. This all is related to the policy and culture of corporate budgeting, so companies dynamically implement policies in accordance with their respective budgeting cultures. Angelia & Rusiti (2014) explained that the preparation of budgeting can be a planning and control tool that can encourage business activities and performance growth opportunities. So that the results of this interview prove that budgeting practiced in a company can affect its sustainability.

Effect of Strategic Decision-Making on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The results of statistical tests have shown that strategic decision-making has a positive effect on the IRI model's sustainability maturity in manufacturing companies in Indonesia as reflected by 0.008 hypothesis p-value for the hypothesis which is smaller than alpha (α) of 0.05. The higher the quality of the analysis of the making of strategic decisions applied in a company, the higher the level of sustainability of the company. On the contrary, the lower the quality of analysis of making strategic decisions applied in a company, the lower the sustainability level of the company.

Managers consider the quality of decisions taken while decisions are also influenced by the quantity of information they have. The information includes advice from their subordinates that can lead to quality decisions and the level of their implementation during implementation (Oriana Negulescu & Elena Doval, 2014). This opinion is also in line with Zahra & Pierce, 1989 who stated that managers in making decisions must listen to the opinions of their subordinates so that the decisions taken can be implemented properly in the company.

This also shows that strategic decision making involves management in terms of determining strategic costs, strategic pricing and brand measurement. Kristisana et al., (2014), said that the company's strategy to improve cost efficiency must pay attention to the opportunities that exist so that more optimal net income can be obtained and then better growth of the company. This is obtained from how the company is able to make all things related to the decision to be taken. So that it can encourage the creation of quality decisions and provide positive impacts on the company's performance in a sustainable manner in the future. In addition, high quality strategic decisions made by company management will increase cost efficiency where it can provide great benefits for the company along with accuracy in the company's ability to capture market opportunities. Mizruchi (1983) in Midiastuti and Mackfudz (2003) explained that the center of the company's operations is on the control of the board of directors. Where the main obligations of the Board of Directors are to keep the company sustainable in the future

The results of the interview also showed that strategic corporate policies taken by managers or the board of directors put the position of the company towards the orientation of achieving long term corporate goals. So that the level of profitability does not only depend on giving dividends to shareholders in the short term over a period of 1 year but also the pressure of companies that encourage long-term oriented policies.

Effects of Competitor Accounting on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The p-value for this hypothesis is 0,000. It is smaller than the alpha value (α) of 0.05. Then H_{a13} is supported, which means that competitor accounting has a positive and significant effect on the IRI of the sustainability maturity model in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. Tandiharjo (2015) also stated that accounting competitors have an influence on organizational performance including also having an influence on competitive advantage. Munizu (2013) stated that organizational performance is much influenced by competitive advantage. Muller (2014) stated that organizational performance is much influenced by competitive advantage.

Various accurate competition mapping is continuously pursued by good companies by analyzing the factors of competitive advantage possessed by competitors in relation to financing methods, pricing and determination of high cost efficiency profitability implemented by competitors, technological sophistication used by competitors, superior training systems performance, education and the company human resources development to continue to contribute

optimally to the organization. The ability to produce meticulous and actual competition analysis of manufacturing companies requires companies to produce periodic analysis and become an important part of the main task in the company's research and development department, the R & D Development, which confirms that there is a close link between a company's competition mapping analysis with tasks and the work of the research and development department which is a key component of the IRI sustainability maturity model. So that the higher the accuracy of the competitor's mapping analysis in the market, the greater the opportunity for the company to be more sustainable. According to Kuntjoroadi & Safitri (2009), the accuracy and ability of companies to measure competitor's cost performance, and measurement of performance and monitoring market position can provide greater opportunities for companies to produce better quality decisions towards improving company performance and thus helping companies to win the competition and encourage growth.

Based on the results of the interview, this study also supports statistical findings that show that the existence of a design team, especially in the research and development department of the company, always regulates the flow of information to and from the company in adapting environmental changes, and seeks to emphasize through policy evaluation activities so that company direction from the output produced by the design team can encourage policies and implementation of company policies to be effective in achieving organizational goals.

Effect of Customer Accounting on the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

Statistical tests have shown that customer accounting has a positive effect on the IRI model's sustainability maturity in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. The significance value of p-value for the hypothesis is 0.002, which is smaller than the alpha value (α) of 0.05. The higher the company's ability to map consumers (corporate strategy in retaining old consumers and adding new consumers), the higher the sustainability of the company. Customer accounting has an important role in fulfilling the many requests from customers and ultimately this can improve the performance and profitability of the company (Xu, X., & Ji, Y. 2016). This also explains that the accuracy and ability of the company in knowing all information about the market and consumers can provide greater opportunities for companies related to the marketing of goods and services. The company's ability can also produce better quality company decisions. Kalalo (2013), said that management and maintenance of relationships between companies and consumers in the long run will encourage the growth of company performance. So, the more maintained the transactional relationship between the company and consumers in the long run, then it will encourage the growth of company performance.

Based on the results of interviews, this study also proves that accuracy in analyzing consumer behavior can provide the ability for companies to encourage the growth and sustainability of the company in the future. This is in line with the research conducted by Valentine (2015) which concluded that there is a significant positive effect of customer accounting and customer orientation on organizational performance.

Effect of IRI Sustainability Maturity Model on Organizational Cultures

Effect of the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model Strategy on Organizational Culture

Statistical tests have shown that the p-value significance for this hypothesis is 0,000, smaller than the alpha value (α) of 0.05, so H_{a15} is accepted/supported. This means, the more consistent the company's sustainability strategy is to be considered and applied, the higher the organizational values that shape organizational culture and vice versa. In order to implement a corporate sustainability strategy, managers need to understand the goals, culture and psychological constraints in organizational change. A better approach to existing organizational change and clear articulation of the objectives of the change will bring desired success (Steven H & Appelbaum Saliba, 2016). So it can be concluded that the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model Strategy influences Organizational Culture in manufacturing companies in Indonesia. Because the manufacturing sector as a capital-based industry is very necessary to implement good corporate governance so that corporate performance improves by also paying attention to environmental, social and resource elements, especially resources which are one of the main sources of exploitation of the company.

Linnenluecke and Griffith (2010) who emphasized the existence of a close relationship between corporate activities that leads to principles and sustainable value with organizational culture, because if all the principles and values of the company have sustainability and are used in all lines eventually will become a culture within the company.

Strict competition pressure, pressure from observers and institutions concerned with the environment, consumers and society influence the company's strategic steps. So that the company's strategy towards how companies consider influential factors is then integrated into policies, practices, use of technology, principles, work procedures, planning and control so that a more sustainable work culture or organizational culture is formed sustainably. As an impact, the consistency and emphasis on policy directions and strategies and company practices positively influence organizational culture, as evidenced in the findings of this study where the stronger the sustainable strategy is practiced, the stronger the culture of the organization.

Based on the results of the interview, the findings also support the results and statistical findings that prove

that the strategy of maturity and sustainability can affect the organization's climate so that it forms its own culture. In this case the organization can achieve its objectives in accordance with the predetermined planning. This achievement has a level of effectiveness, and high efficiency. The company also has measurement standards to measure the level of success of the company by continuously updating and evaluating the performance of its organization. The organizational climate which was emphasized in strategic steps and policies was carried out consistently which in the end further strengthened its organizational culture towards a more sustainable organization.

Effect of the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model Design Tool on Organizational Culture

Statistical testing has shown that the IRI sustainability model design tool has a positive effect on organizational culture in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. The significance value of p-value of 0,000 is smaller than the alpha value (α) of 0.05, so H_0 is accepted, which means the IRI design device for sustainability maturity model has a positive and significant effect on organizational culture. The stronger the company's sustainability design tools are implemented, the higher the organizational values that shape organizational culture. On the contrary the lower the company's sustainability sustainability design tools are applied, the lower organizational values that shape organizational culture. This is supported by research result conducted by Kimberly Elsbach and Ileana Stiglia (2018) that there is a connection between the design of a product and organizational culture. Linnenluecke and Griffith (2010) emphasized the existence of a close relationship between corporate activities that lead to principles and sustainable value with organizational culture, because if all the principles and values of the company are sustainable and are used in all lines, it eventually will become a culture within the company.

The results of the interview show that departments or divisions formed for R & D and NPD activities make the achievement of corporate goals become effective because special divisions with special teams dynamically influence other activities and even influence company direction and policies. This happens because R & D and NPD activities are used as technical references for companies as long as performance activities take place in achieving their goals so that they are effective, efficient, high productivity, and high sustainable. The scope of R & D and NPD which is not only focused on product development causes the scope that is affected to be very large and wide. Environmental and supply chain activities have been the scope of discussion and research on R & D activities in the manufacturing sector in Indonesia. So that many manufacturing companies have green product nuances as evidence of the broad role of R & D and NPD in manufacturing companies in Indonesia.

Conclusions, Implications, Limitations, Suggestions

Conclusion

1. Dimensions of corporate governance variables IRI Sustainability Maturity Model

The independent board of commissioners and board of directors each have a positive influence on the IRI sustainability maturity model. However, the dimensions of independent directors and audit committees do not affect the IRI of the sustainability maturity model in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. The positive influence of the independent board of commissioners on the IRI sustainability maturity model is found on the high level of independence of the commissioners regardless of the various interests of shareholders and the board of directors. The Independent Board of Commissioners sees everything from various aspects so that the independent board of commissioners always adopts all the interests of a broader stakeholder. While carrying out their duties and responsibilities, the independent board of commissioners produces proposals and policies that encourage more sustainable corporate business activities.

2. Dimensions of Corporate Governance variables on Strategic Management Accounting

Independent board of commissioners and board of directors have a positive effect on strategic management accounting in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. However, independent directors and audit committees have no effect on strategic management accounting in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. The positive influence of the independent board of commissioners on strategic management accounting is found if the independence of the independent board of commissioners is well maintained, which then influenced the process of making independent commissioners' decisions to encourage the company's strategic steps. Proposals from the independent board of commissioners so that the company pays attention to the interests of stakeholders more broadly provides capabilities and capabilities for companies to make strategic analysis both in understanding and determining costs, mapping competition, consumer behavior to understand consumer needs and expectations and compile a systematic report from a series of strategic analyzes carried out by the company to be reported to stakeholders. Therefore, as found in this study the independence of commissioners demand more strategic business processes that can be applied by the company.

3. The dimensions of the strategic management accounting variable—strategic costing, strategic planning, control and performance, budgeting, strategic decision making, customer accounting and competitors accounting on the IRI sustainability maturity model

The dimensions of the strategic management accounting variable, namely strategic costing, strategic planning, control and performance, budgeting, strategic decision making, customer accounting and accounting competitors each have a positive effect on the IRI sustainability maturity model in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. The influence of the dimensions of strategic costing, strategic planning, control and performance, budgeting, strategic decision making, customer accounting and competitors accounting of the IRI sustainability maturity model is found in Indonesia manufacturing companies. Especially in carrying out its strategic steps where each strategy is practiced and carried out in an integrated manner in all aspects and all components. As found in this study, manufacturing companies carry out strategic analysis steps both in the perspective of costing, planning, controlling, budgeting, decision-making processes and in measuring consumer behavior to determine the needs, expectations and levels of customer satisfaction towards the company's products and accuracy in providing an overview and information about competition mapping, markets, market behavior and the factors that influence it. As a result, design and strategic design tools are applied in the company such as creating a special team that analyzes the company's strategy, including the establishment of company R & D with regard to product and market development strategies targeted by the company. The R & D formed by the company is the impact of the company's efforts to implement strategic measures, which prove a strong and positive relationship between strategic management practices and the company's efforts to improve corporate sustainability.

4. Dimensions of IRI Variables Sustainability maturity model towards organizational culture

The IRI variable sustainability maturity model has a positive and significant effect on organizational culture in registered manufacturing companies in Indonesia. The positive influence of IRI on the sustainability maturity model on organizational culture has been found in this sustainability model which uses the IRI Sustainability Maturity Model. This use will give manufacturing companies specific capabilities within an organization from time to time slowly but surely in a form that is long term oriented so that finally it creates a firm culture of corporate performance and becomes the company's competitive advantage in culture. The creation of sustainable business practices that are carried out consistently, continuously and from time to time through the establishment of rules, the formation of strategies and design tools that determine the direction of corporate sustainability then becomes values that are adopted and practiced by all levels and members of the organization and then creates sustainable based organizational culture. So that sustainability-oriented planning, implementation, control becomes the pattern, characteristics and specific identity of a company, which in the long run becomes a culture. It has been proven in research that the IRI sustainability maturity model has a positive and significant effect on organizational culture in registered companies in Indonesia. The more consistent and strict the sustainability orientation of a company, the more inherent and unique identity and shape of the organization's culture.

Managerial Implications

Based on the findings in this study, this study has the following implications:

1. Managerial implications for companies are the need for clear supervision and rules regarding good corporate governance practices in manufacturing companies. The forms of supervision which are made, among others, tightening the requirements for independent directors and audit committees selection by taking into account the elements of individual and educational background, work experience and areas of expertise. This is done so that selected independent directors and audit committees can take part in making decisions made by the company's board of directors.
2. In order to avoid the existence of agency conflict between the independent director and the audit committee of the board of directors, the board of directors needs to start giving trust to the independent director and the audit committee. By doing so the independent directors and audit committees can carry out their role as agents of governance. It is expected then that the independent directors and audit committees will play a major role in the decisions taken in accordance with the Circular Letter of the Indonesia Stock Exchange No. SE-00001 / BEI / 02-2014
3. The managerial implication for the government is that it must include elements of education, work experience and areas of expertise in the stakeholder's related legislation especially for those who will serve as independent commissioners, independent directors and audit committees.

Research Limitations

This research has a number of limitations. It is expected that these limitations can be improved by the next researcher who conducts research that links corporate governance, IRI sustainability maturity model, strategic management accounting and organizational culture. The few limitations of this study are:

1. Respondents are only from a number of companies engaged in the manufacturing sector which are listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Therefore, the results have not been able to be generalized widely in the context of non-manufacturing companies.

2. In conducting the interview process, the respondent only wants to answer the questions in the list of questions for reasons of limited time and of company confidentiality.
3. The company sample used still has strong intervention from the BOD towards the independent commissioner and independent director.

Suggestion

As an implication of the limitations in this study, then to examine the results of this study, the following points are suggested to future research:

1. Establish strict criteria related to the selection of independent directors and audit committees, which are expected to be able to maintain their independence and objectivity towards decisions taken so that the decisions taken can be accounted for to shareholders.
2. The board of directors should increase the number of small meetings or meetings about company operations so that they can reduce suspicions about the performance of Independent directors.
3. The board of directors should always update matters related to the plans and strategies that will be carried out by the company to the audit committee, so that they also have a broader knowledge of the company.
4. For further researchers, in order to be able to see the independence of the board of directors, independent commissioners and independent directors and audit committees, it is expected to be able to use samples in accordance with the board of directors, independent commissioners, independent directors and audit committees competencies.

REFERENCE

- i. Agung, A.M., Lilik. (2007). *Budaya Perusahaan ke Budaya Kerja, dalam buku Corporate Culture, Challenge to Excellence*. Jakarta: PT. Elex Media Komputindo.
- ii. Agwu ME. 2018. "Analysis of the Impact of Strategic Management on the Business Performance of SMEs in Nigeria" *Academy of strategic management journal* Vol: 17 Issue: 1
- iii. Ahmad, M., Anjum, T., & Azeem, M. (2014). *Investigating the Impact of Corporate Governance on Earning Management in the Presense of Firm Size; Evidence from Pakistan*. *International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 3(2): 89-90.
- iv. Alqatamin, R.M. (2018). *Audit Committee Effectiveness and Company Performance: Evidence from Jordan*. *Accounting and Finance Research*, 7(2): 48-60.
- v. Alsoboa, S. (2015). *Practices of Competitor Accounting and Its Influence on the Competitive Advantages: An Empirical Study in Jordanian Manufacturing Companies*. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: Accounting and Auditing*, 15(3): 1-13.
- vi. Alsoboa, S., Al-Ghazzawi, A., & Joudeh, A. (2015). *The Impact of Strategic Costing Techniques on the Performance of Jordanian Listed Manufacturing Companies*. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(10): 116-127.
- vii. Angelia, V., & Rusiti, C.H. (2014). *Penyusunan Penganggaran Operasional Sebagai Alat Perencanaan dan Pengendalian Pada Home Industry "Jogjakart"*. *e-Journal Universitas Atma Jaya Yogyakarta*, 1-15.
- viii. Akhtar, Shamshad. (2006). *Syariah Compliant Corporate Governance*. Keynote address by the governor of the State Bank of Pakistan at the annual Corporate Governance Conference, Dubai, United Arab Emirates.
- ix. Akicho, J.O., Oloko, M., & Kihoro, J.M. (2016). *Influence of Leadership Charater and Risk Management as Forms of Governance Practices on Performance in Kenya's Public Sector: A Survey of Selected National Government Ministries*. *European Journal of Business Management*, 5(1): 43-64.
- x. Albino, V., Balice, A., Dangelico, R. M., and Iacobone, F. A. (2012). *The effect of the adoption of environmental strategies on green product development: A study of companies on world sustainability indices*. *International Journal of Management* 29 (2): 525-538.
- xi. Amabile, T.M (1983). "The Social Psychology of Creativity: A Componential Conceptualization" *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 45: 357- 376
- xii. Amabile, T. (1996). "Assessing the Work Environment for Creativity": *Academy of Management Journal*, 39(5), 1154-1184.
- xiii. Amabile, T. M. (1998). "How to kill creativity": *Harvard Business Review*, September/October, 77-87
- xiv. Almatari, Y.A., Al-Swidi, A.K., Fadzil, F.H., & Al-Matari, E.M. (2012). *Board of Directors, Audit Committee Characteristics and Performance of Saudi Arabia Listed Companies*. *International Review of Management*

and Marketing, 2(4): 241-251.

- xv. Alnasser, S.A.S., & Muhammed, J. (2012). *Introduction to Corporate Governance from Islamic Perspective. Humanomics*, 28(3): 220-231.
- xvi. Aquilera, R., Florackis, C., & Kim, H. (2016). *Advancing the Corporate Governance, Research Agenda. Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 24(3): 172-180.
- xvii. Appelbaum, S.H., Calcagno, R., Magarelli, S.M., & Saliba, M. (2016). *A Relationship Between Corporate Sustainability and Organizational Change. Industrial and Commercial Training*, 48(3): 133-141.
- xviii. Arunruangsirilert, T., & Chonglertham, S. (2017). *Effect of Corporate Governance Characteristics on Strategic Management Accounting in Thailand. Asian Review of Accounting*, 25(1): 85-105.
- xix. Babafemi, I.D. (2015). *Corporate Strategy, Planning and Performance Evaluation: A Survey of Literature. Journal of Management Policies and Practices*, 3(1): 43-49.
- xx. Barter, N. (2011). *Stakeholder Theory: Pictures, the Environment and Sustainable Development – do We Have a Good Enough Picture in Our Heads or Do We Need Something Different? Asia Pacific Work In Progress Research Papers Series*, 4: 1-17.
- xxi. Bassiouny, S.W. (2016). *The Impact of Firm Characteristics on Earnings Management: An Empirical Study on the Listed Firms in Egypt. Journal of Business and Retail Management Research (JBRMR)*, 10(3): 34-45.
- xxii. Baydoun, N., Maguire, W., Ryan, N., & Willett, R. (2014). *Corporate Governance in Five Arabian Gulf Countries. Managerial Auditing Journal*, 28(1): 7-22.
- xxiii. Berdufi, N., and Dushi, D. (2015). *Social Contract and the Governments Legitimacy. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(6): 392-398.
- xxiv. Berger, P.D., Bolton, R.N., Bowman, D., Briggs, E., Kumar, V., Parasuraman, A., & Terry, C. (2002). *Marketing actions and the value of customer assets: A framework for customer asset management. Journal of Service Research*, 5: 39-54.
- xxv. Bodroastuti, T. (2009). *Pengaruh Struktur Corporate Governance terhadap Financial Distress. E-Journal Widya Manggala*, 16(32): 1-15.
- xxvi. Boeva, B., & Stoychev, I. *Corporate Governance and the Sustainable Development. European Journal of Economics and Business Studies*, 3(1): 45-55.
- xxvii. Bolton, R.N., Lemon, K.N., & Verhoef, P.C. (2004). *The theoretical underpinnings of customer asset management: A framework and propositions for future research. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 32: 271-292.
- xxviii. Brey, C., and Haavaldsen, M. (2014). *Exploring the Relationship Between Sustainability Disclosure, Financial Performance and Initial Public Offerings. Master's Thesis, MSc International Business, Copenhagen Business School.*
- xxix. Cadez, S. and Guilding, C. (2012). *Strategy, strategic management accounting and performance: a configurational analysis. Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 112(3): 484-501.
- xxx. Chenhall, R.H. and Langfield-Smith, K. (2003). *Performance measurement and reward systems, trust, and strategic change. Journal of Management Accounting Research*, 15(1): 117.
- xxxi. Cynthia. (2015). *Pengaruh Strategi Costing Sebagai Strategic Management Accounting Techniques terhadap Competitive Advantage dan Organizational Performance. Business Accounting Review*, 3(1): 1-27.
- xxxii. Choudry, M.A., & Hoque, M.Z. (2006). *Corporate Governance in Islamic Perspective. Corporate Governance*, 6(2): 116-128.
- xxxiii. Dalton, D., Ellstrand, & Johnson. (1998). *Meta-analytic reviews of Board Composition, Leadership Structure and Financial Performance. Strategic Management Journal*, (19): 269-290.
- xxxiv. Donaldson, L., & Davis, J.H. (1991). *Stewardship Theory or Agency Theory: CEO Governance and Shareholder Returns. Research Article*, 16(1): 342-364.
- xxxv. Dudovskiy, J. (2017). *Samsung Organizational Culture: Seniority-Oriented Culture That Needs to Change. Sumber: <https://research-methodology.net/samsung-organizational-culture-seniority-oriented-culture-needs-change/>.*

- xxxvi. Eccles, R.G., Ioannou, I., & Serafeim, G. (2011). *The Impact of a Corporate Culture of Sustainability on Corporate Behavior and Performance*. Working Paper, 12(35): 1-56.
- xxxvii. Galpin, T., Whittington, J.L., & Bell, G. (2014). *Is Your Sustainability Strategy Sustainable? Creating a Culture of Sustainability*. *Corporate Governance*, 15(1): 1-17.
- xxxviii. Geroski, P., and S. Machin. 1992. *Do Innovating Firms Out perform Non-Innovators?*. *Business Strategy Review* 3 (2):79-90
- xxxix. Geroski, P. A., and S. Toker. 1996. *The turnover of market leaders in UK manufacturing industry, 1979-86*. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*14 (2):141-158
- xl. Ghazali, I. (2016). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 21*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- xli. Goh, S., & Richards, G. (1997). *Benchmarking the Learning Capability of Organizations*. *European Management Journal*, 15(5): 575-583.
- xlii. Gomez, J.M., Lagos, D., & Betancourt, G.G. (2017). *Effect of the Board of Directors on Firm Performance*. *International Journal of Economic Research*, 14(6): 349-361.
- xliii. Guilding, C. (1999). *Competitor-focused accounting: an exploratory note*. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 24(7): 583-595.
- xliv. Guo, L., Smallman, C., & Radford, J. (2013). *A Critique of Corporate Governance in China*. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 55(4): 257-272.
- xlv. Haider, N., Khan, N., & Iqbal, N. (2015). *Impact of Corporate Governance on Firm Financial Performance in Islamic Financial Institution*. *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences*, 51: 106-110.
- xlvi. Haneas, K., Arthur, D., Balagopal, B., Kong, M. T., Reeves, M., Velken, I., Hopkins, M. S., and Kruschwitz, N. (2011). *Sustainability: The “embracers” seize advantage*. *MIT Sloan, Management Review*, 1-13.
- xlvii. Harmoni, A. (2013). *Stakeholder-Based Analysis of Sustainability Report: A Case Study on Mining Companies in Indonesia*, *International Conference Eurasian Economies*, 204-210.
- xlviii. Haryanto, Y.P. (2015). *Pengaruh Hubungan Corporate Governance terhadap Kinerja Keuangan*. *Diponegoro Journal of Accounting*, 4(2): 1-15.
- xlix. Heralova, R.S. (2017). *Life Cycle Costing as An Important Contribution to Feasibility Study in Construction Projects*. *Procedia Engineering*, 196: 565-570.
- l. Hermawan, A.A. (2011). *The Influence of Effective Board of Commissioners and Audit Committee on the Informativeness of Earnings: Evidence from Indonesia Listed Firms*. *Asia Pacific Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 2(1): 1-38.
- li. Honggowati, S., Rahmawati, R., Aryani, Y.A., & Probohudono, A.N. (2017). *Corporate Governance and Strategic Management Accounting Disclosure*. *Indonesian Journal of Sustainability Accounting and Management*, 1(1): 23-30.
- lii. Huillier, B.M. (2014). *What Does “Corporate Governance” Actually Mean?* *Corporate Governance*, 14(3): 300-319.
- liii. Husin, M.A., & Ibrahim, M.D. (2016). *The Role of Accounting Services and Impact on Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Performance in Manufacturing Sector from East Coast Region of Malaysia: A Conceptual Paper*. *Procedia-Social and Behaviour Sciences*, 115: 54-67.
- liv. Hynds, E.J., Brand, V., Burek, S., Jager, W., Knox, P., Parker, J.P., Schwartz, L., Taylor, J., & Zeitlow, M. (2014). *A Maturity Model for Sustainability in New Product Development*. *Research Technology Management*, 50-57.
- lv. IFAC. (2018). *Enterprise Governance: Getting the Balance Right*, *International Federation of Accountants*. Australia: Sydney.
- lvi. Ikechukwu A. (2016). *The Use of Strategic Management Accounting Techniques (SMATs) in Sustainability Performance Measurement for Corporate Governance in Nigeria*. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(3): 262–271.

- lvii. ISO 14051. (2011). *Environmental Management-Material Flow Cost Accounting-General Framework*. Sumber: <https://www.iso.org/standard/50986.html>.
- lviii. Jakobsen, M. (2012). *Intra-organizational Management Accounting for Inter-Organizational Control during Negotiation Processes*. *Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management*, 9(2): 96-122.
- lix. Jensen, M.C., & Meckling, W.H. (1976). *Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure*. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4): 305-360.
- lx. Joshi & Li. (2016). *What is Corporate Sustainability and How Do Firms Practice It? A Management Accounting Research Perspective*. *Journal of Management Accounting Research*, 28(2): 1-11.
- lxi. Kalalo, R.E. (2013). *Customer Relationship Management dan Kualitas Pelayanan Pengaruhnya terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen PT. Matahari Dept. Store, Manado*. *Jurnal EMBA*, 1(4): 1553-1561.
- lxii. Kartika, V., Budiharto, Mahmudah, S. (2017). *Tanggungjawab Direksi Dalam Hal Terjadi Transaksi Afiliasi Yang Mengandung Benturan Kepentingan Pada Kasus PT. Sumalindo Lestari Jaya Tbk. Diponegoro Law Journal*, 6(2): 1-20.
- lxiii. Kementerian Perindustrian Republik Indonesia. (2015). *Laporan Kinerja Kementerian Perindustrian 2015*. <http://www.kemenperin.go.id/download/10591/Laporan-Kinerja-Kementerian-Perindustrian-Tahun-2015>.
- lxiv. Ketschau, T.J. (2015). *Social Justice as a Link Between Sustainability and Educational Sciences*. *Open Access Sustainability Journal*, 7: 1-18.
- lxv. Khan, M.M. and Jain, P.K. (2010). *Management Accounting: Text, Problems and Causes*. New Delhi: McGraw-Hill.
- a. Kim et al. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity* (2016) 2:5
- lxvi. Kosnik, R.D. (1990). *Effects of Board Demography and Directors' Incentive on Corporate Greenmail Decision*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(1): 129-150.
- lxvii. Krause & Semadeni. (2013). *Apprentice, Departure, and Demotion: An Examination of the Three Types of CEO-Board Chair Separation*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(3): 1-15.
- lxviii. Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2014). *Organizational Behavioral Ed. 5*. Boston: McGraw-Hill.
- lxix. Kristisana, Y., Suhadak, & Dwiatmanto. (2014). *Analisis Biaya Standar Untuk Mendukung Efisiensi Biaya Produksi Perusahaan*. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 13(2): 1-8.
- lxx. Kuntjoroadi, W., & Safitri, N. (2009). *Analisis Strategi Bersaing dalam Persaingan Usaha Penerbangan Komersial*. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi dan Organisasi*, 16(1): 45-52.
- lxxi. Lahindah, L. (2015). *Proses Pengambilan Keputusan Strategik Pada Usaha Kecil Menengah: Sebuah Kajian Literatur*. *Finance & Accounting Journal*, 04(01): 153-172.
- lxxii. Larker, D.F., & Tayan, B. (2016). *Chairman and CEO: The Controversy Over Board Leadership Structure*. *Stanford Closer Look Series*, 1-11.
- lxxiii. Lawrence, S., Collins, E. & Roper, J. (2013). *Expanding responsibilities of corporate governance: The incorporation of CSR and sustainability*. *Indian Journal of Corporate Governance*, 6(1): 49-63.
- lxxiv. Lewis, G. (2016). *In-Depth: Independent Board Chairman*. 1-5.
- lxxv. Li, W., Xu, Y., Niu, J., & Qiu, A. (2012). *A Survey of Corporate Governance: International Trends and China's Mode*. *Nankai Business Review*, 3(1): 4-30.
- lxxvi. Linnenluecke, M., & Griffiths, A. (2010). *Corporate Sustainability and Organizational Culture*. *Journal of World Business*, 45: 357-366.
- lxxvii. Liu, Y.S., Zhou, X., Yang, J.H., & Hoepner, A.G.F. (2016). *Corporate Carbon Emission and Financial Performance: Does Carbon Disclosure Mediate the Relationship in the UK?*. *Discussion Paper*, 03: 1-42.
- lxxviii. Lukas, S., & Basuki, B. (2015). *The Implementation of Good Corporate Governance and Its Impact on the Financial Performance of Banking Industry Listed in IDX*. *The International Journal of Accounting and Business Society*, 23(1): 47-72.
- lxxix. M.A.Musa et.,all, (2008) "Corporate governance and innovative leaders", *Social Responsibility*

- lxxx. Mahar, M., & Andersson, T. (2008) *Corporate Governance: Effects on Firm Performance and Economic Growth*. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 25: 351-405.
- lxxxi. Majeed, S., Aziz, T., Saleem, S.(2015). *The effect of corporate governance elements on corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure: An empirical evidence from listed companies at KSE Pakistan*. *Int. J. Finance*, 3: 530–556.
- lxxxii. Majeed A., Al-Maryani, H., Sadi, H.H. (2012). *Strategic Management Accounting Techniques in Romanian Companies: Some Survey Evidence*. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 3: 387 – 396
- lxxxiii. Makhrus, M. (2011). *Pengaruh Komite Audit terhadap Kinerja Perusahaan Melalui Manajemen Laba Sebagai Variabel Intervening*. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Keuangan Islam*, 53-77.
- lxxxiv. Mangkunegara, A.P. (2014). *Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- lxxxv. Manyika, J., Sinclair, J., Dobbs, R., Strube, G., Rassey, L., Mischke, J., Remes, J., Roxburgh, C., George, K., O'Halloran, D., & Ramaswamy, S. (2012). *Manufacturing the future: The next era of global growth and innovation*. McKinsey Operation Practice. Sumber: https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Business%20Functions/Operations/Our%20Insights/The%20future%20of%20manufacturing/MGI_Manufacturing%20the%20future_Executive%20summary_Nov%202012.ashx.
- lxxxvi. Marota, M., Marimin, M., & Sasongko, H. (2015). *Perancangan dan Penerapan Material Flow Cost Accounting untuk Peningkatan Keberlanjutan Perusahaan PT Xyz*. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Agribisnis*, 12(2): 92-105.
- a. Mason, G., K. Bishop, and C. Robinson. 2009. *Business Growth and Innovation: The wider impact of rapidly-growing firms in UK city-regions*, edited by NESTA. London.
- lxxxvii. Masrukhin dan Waridin. (2006). *Pengaruh Motivasi, Kepuasan, Budaya Organisasi dan Kepemimpinan terhadap Kinerja Pegawai*. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 7(2): 1-21.
- lxxxviii. Michael, B., & Goo, S.H. (2015). *Corporate Governance and Its Reform in Hong Kong: A Study in Comparative Corporate Governance*. *Corporate Governance*, 15(4): 444-475.
- lxxxix. Midiastuty, P.P., dan Machfoedz, M. (2003). *Analisis Hubungan Mekanisme Corporate Governance dan Indikasi Manajemen Laba*. *Simposium Nasional Akuntansi VI*, pp. 1-21.
- xc. Muller, V.O. (2014). *The Impact of Board Composition on the Financial Performance of FTSE 100 Constituents*. *2nd World Conference On Business, Economics and Management, Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 109: 969-975.
- xc. Natasha, P., & Devie. (2013). *Analisa Pengaruh Strategic Planning Terhadap Keunggulan Bersaing dan Kinerja Perusahaan*. *Business Accounting Review*, 1(2): 185-196.
- xcii. Negulescu, N., & Doval, E. (2014). *The Quality Of Decision Making Process Related to Organizations effectiveness*. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 15: 858-863.
- a. Nixon, B., & Burns, J. (2012). *The paradox of strategic management accounting*. *Management Accounting Research*, 23, 229-244
- xciii. Nuhu, M.S., Umaru, S.Y., & Salisu, S. (2017). *The Effect of Audit Committee's Quality on the Financial Performance of Food and Beverages Industry in Nigeria*. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 6(9): 32-40.
- xciv. Obioma, B.K., Uchenna, N., & Alexanda, K.O.U. (2015). *The Effect of Industrial Development on Economic Growth (An Empirical Evidence in Nigeria 1973-2013)*. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 4(2): 127-140.
- xcv. Parente, T.C., & Filho, C.A.P.M. (2016). *Corporate Social Responsibility: Perceptions of Directors in Brazil*. *Management Research Review*, 39(11): 1472-1493.
- xcvi. Parminter, T.G., Wilson, J.A. (2003). *Strategies to encourage adoption: a case study of New Zealand farmers*. ISSN 0370-2731. Pp:66-68.
- xcvii. Peterlin et. al (2015). *Strategic Decision Making For Organizational Sustainability: The Implications Of Servant Leadership and Sustainable leadership Approaches*. *Economic and Business Review*, 17(3): 27-37.

- xcviii. Pesamaa, O., Klaesson, J., & Haahti, A. (2008). *Board of Directors and Its Effect on Performance: The Case of Gnosjo Region in Sweden*. *Innovative Marketing*, 4(4): 77-85.
- xcix. Popesko, B., Novak, P., Dvorsky, J., & Papadaki, S. (2017). *The Maturity of a Budgeting System and Its Influence on Corporate Performance*. *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, 14(7): 91-104.
- c. Pratama, A.N., Suhadak & Topowijono. (2012). *Pengaruh Penerapan Good Corporate Governance terhadap Kinerja Keuangan*. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, (2): 1-6.
- ci. Putra, B.P.D. (2015). *Pengaruh Dewan Komisaris, Proporsi Komisaris Independen, terhadap Kinerja Perusahaan*. *Jurnal Manajemen Teori dan Terapan*, 8(2): 70-85.
- cii. Ratnatunga, J. and Alam, M. (2011). *Strategic governance and management accounting: evidence from a case study*. *Abacus: A Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business Studies*, 47(3): 343-382.
- ciii. Rifai, B. (2009). *Peran Komisaris Independen dalam Mewujudkan Good Corporate Governance di Perusahaan Publik*. *Jurnal hukum*, 3(16): 396-412.
- civ. Risa. (2014). *Pengaruh Partisipasi Penyusunan Anggaran dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Senjangan Anggaran*. *JRAK*, 5(2): 1-20.
- cv. Robbins, SP., & Judge. (2015). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- cvi. Roslender, R. and Hart, S.J. (2002). *Integrating management accounting and marketing in the pursuit of competitive advantage: the case for strategic management accounting*. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 13(2): 255-277.
- cvii. Sabbaghi, O. (2016). *Corporate Governance in China: A Review*. *Corporate Governance*, 16(5): 866-882.
- cviii. Sarens, G., & Merendino, A. (2016). *Multiple Agency Theory in Corporate Governance: An Alternative Lens to Study Independent commissioner*. *Louvain School of Management Research Institut*, 1-30.
- cix. Sandalgaard, N., & Bukh, P.N. (2014). *Beyond Budgeting and Change: A Case Study*. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*, 10(3): 409-423.
- cx. Schiller, S. (2010). *Management Accounting in A Learning Environment*. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*, 6(1): 123-148.
- cxii. Seal, W. (2006). *Management accounting and corporate governance: an institutional interpretation of the agency problem*. *Management Accounting Research*, 17(4): 389-408.
- cxiii. Shah, H., Malik, A. & Malik, M.S. (2011). *Strategic management accounting – a messiah for management accounting*. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1(4): 1-7.
- cxiiii. Shareia, B.F. (2015). *Theories of Development*. *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 2(1): 78-90.
- cxv. Smith, S.S. (2017). *Strategic Management Accounting – A Strategic Role for Accountancy*. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 8(2): 4-15.
- cxvi. Smith, S.S. (2014). *Integrated Reporting, Corporate Governance and the Future of the Accounting Function*. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(10): 58-63.
- cxvii. Srivastava et al., (2018) "Corporate governance: mapping the change", *International Journal of Law and Management*, Vol. 60 Issue: 1, pp.19-33
- cxviii. Sugiyono. (2016). *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- cxix. Swastika, D.L.T. (2013). *Corporate Governance, Firm Size, and Earning Management: Evidence in Indonesia Stock Exchange*. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 10(4): 77-82.
- cx. Tandiharjo, A.H., & Devie. (2015). *Pengaruh Competitor Accounting Sebagai Strategic Management Accounting Techniques terhadap Competitive Advantage and Organizational Performance*. *Business Accounting Review*, 3(1): 168-179.
- cxii. Tapinos, E., Dyson, R.G., & Meadows, M. (2005). *The Impact of Performance Measurement in Strategic Planning*. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 54(5/6): 370-384.
- cxiii. Tatarusanu, M., & Onea, A.N. (2016). *Organizational Culture and Values for Corporate*

- cxxii. Topak, M.S. (2011). *The Effect of Board Size on Firm Performance: Evidence from Turkey*. *Middle Eastern Finance and Economics*, 14: 119-127.
- cxxiii. Tuan, L.T. (2014). *Corporate Governance and Brand Performance*. *Management Research Review*, 37(1): 45-68.
- cxxiv. Tuomela, T.-S. (2005). *The interplay of different levers of control: a case study of introducing a new performance measurement system*. *Management Accounting Research*, 16(3): 293-320.
- cxxv. Tayles, M., Bramley, A., Adshead, N., & Farr, J. (2002). *Dealing with the management of intellectual capital: The potential role of strategic management accounting*. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 15, 251-267.
- cxxvi. Tayles, M., Pike, R.H., & Sofian, S. (2007). *Intellectual capital, management accounting practices and corporate performance: Perceptions of managers*. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 20, 522- 548
- cxxvii. Ussahawanitchakit, P. (2017). *Customer Accounting as a Valuable Approach of Strategic Management Accounting: Evidence from Hotel Business in Thailand*. *E-Journal of Mahasarakham Business School*, 1-21.
- cxxviii. Wickramasinghe, D. and Alawattage, C. (2007). *Management Accounting Change: Approaches and Perspectives*/Danture Wickramasinghe and Chandana Alawattage. New York: Routledge.
- cxxix. Widyati, M.F. (2013). *Pengaruh Dewan Direksi, Komisaris Independen, Komite Audit, Kepemilikan Manajerial dan Kepemilikan Institusional terhadap Kinerja Keuangan*. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 1(1): 234-249.
- xxx. Wijayanti, S., & Mutmainah, S. (2012). *Pengaruh Penerapan Corporate Governance terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Perbankan yang Terdaftar di Bursa Efek Indonesia 2009*. *Journal Of Accounting*, 1(1): 3-17.
- xxxi. Wijethilake, C., Ekanayake, A., & Perere, S. (2015). *Board Involvement in Corporate Performance: Evidence from a Developing Country*. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 5(3): 250-268.
- xxxii. Wilson, R.M.S. (2013). *Strategic management accounting*, in David Ashton, T.H. and Scapens, R.W. (Eds), *Issues in Management Accounting*, 2nd ed., Chapter 8. London: Prentice Hall, London, 159-190.
- xxxiii. Woodman, R. W., Sawyer, J. E & Griffin, R. W. (1993). *Toward a theory of organizational creativity*. *Academy of Management Review*, 18: 293 321
- xxxiv. Yasuda, T. 2005. "Firm Growth, Size, Age and Behavior in Japanese Manufacturing" : *Small Business Economics* 24,:1-15"
- xxxv. Yu, M. (2011). *Analyst Recommendations and Corporate Governance in Emerging Markets*. *International Journal of Accounting and Information Management*, 19(1): 34-52.
- xxxvi. Zahra, S.A., & Pearce, J.A. (1989). *Boards of directors and corporate financial performance: A review and integrative model*. *J. Manag.*, (15): 291–334.
- xxxvii. Zhang, P. (2010). *Board Information and Strategic Tasks Performance*. *Corporate Governance, An International Review*, 18(5): 473-487